

Detection of microplastics using inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) operated in single-event mode

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Abstract

The occurrence of microplastics in many, if not all environmental compartments is a matter of increasing concern and deserves proper attention. However, there is still a lack of analytical tools for straightforward monitoring of these tiny plastic particles at environmentally relevant levels in waters. Inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) operated in single-particle mode (SP-ICP-MS) was demonstrated to be a powerful technique for the characterization of metallic nanoparticles, but to the best of the authors' knowledge, SP-ICP-MS has not yet been evaluated for the purpose of detection of microplastics and their quantitative determination (particle number density). In this work, spherical polystyrene microspheres of 1 and 2.5 μm – to mimic microplastics coming from plastic waste – have been detected using ICP-MS. The approach developed relies on the ultra-fast monitoring of transient signals (with a dwell time of 100 μs) when using a quadrupole-based ICP-MS unit in so-called single-event mode and registering the signal spikes produced by individual microparticles by monitoring the signal intensity at a mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) of 13 ($^{13}\text{C}^+$). The accuracy of the number-based concentration results (particle number densities) has been assessed by comparing the number of events detected when monitoring $^{13}\text{C}^+$ to those detected when monitoring $^{165}\text{Ho}^+$ for 2.5 μm lanthanide-doped polystyrene beads. Additionally, the results obtained for both polystyrene microspheres in terms of size (most frequently occurring intensity of the signal distribution) compare well with the size as determined using electron microscopy. ICP-MS operated in single-event mode thus allows information on both the size distribution and mass concentration of microplastics to be obtained. As this approach makes use of instrumentation already available in many routine labs analyzing environmental samples, it can enable these labs to address microplastics by using their instrument in single-event mode.

Keywords:

Microplastics, nanoplastics, single-particle inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry SP-ICP-MS

Introduction

The exceptional properties of plastics, such as their chemical, light- and temperature-resistance, in combination with the low cost and ease of manufacturing have rendered them into one of the most popular and widely used materials over the last decades. The widespread use of plastics in everyday life has triggered an increasing global production, unfortunately also accompanied by a significant accumulation of plastic litter in the environment.¹ In 2017, it was reported that approximately 6,300 million tons of plastic waste were generated between 1950 and 2015, around 5,000 million tons of which accumulated in landfills and the natural environment.² The environmental litter can undergo weathering processes, such as fragmentation and degradation, generating smaller particles.³ The plastics have been classified based on their size by different authors and/or organizations, although no final harmonized definition has been issued so far.⁴ In general, microplastics (MPs) are considered to have a size range between 1 μm and 5 mm (< 5 mm), while the term nanoplastics (NPs) is preferred when the size is < 1 μm . For MPs, an additional distinction has been suggested between small (1 μm – 1 mm) and large (1 mm – 5 mm) MPs.⁵ It needs to be noted that while the plastic litter comprising large plastic pieces can be “easily” removed and recycled, the removal of the small plastic particles is much more difficult and in many instances even impossible. Therefore, there is a raising concern about the ecological impact, especially that caused by these small plastic pieces (< 5 mm), as they show a larger surface-to-size ratio, potentially enhancing the adsorption of contaminants and increasing their bioavailability to biota.^{6, 7} In the case of small MPs and NPs, the effects can be even worse due to their possibility to cross biological barriers, to penetrate tissues and to accumulate in organs. As a result, MPs may exert severe adverse effects in different environmental compartments and on human health.⁸

Nowadays, understanding the fate, transport and risks associated with MPs in the environment is an important scientific challenge and is of crucial concern due to the exponentially increasing amounts of these materials in, among other, the oceans.^{9, 10} Thus, there is a need for the development of suitable and straightforward methodologies for the detection, quantification and characterization of MPs in order to control this globally emerging threat.^{11, 12}

Over the last years, different analytical procedures have already been proposed for the determination of MPs, although the lack of standardization and traceability makes inter-comparison of different studies nearly impossible. The gap between the needs and the analytical capabilities is even far more pronounced in the case of small MPs and NPs.^{5, 13}

As is the case for MPs, metallic engineered nanoparticles (ENPs) are small entities that have gained increasing attention during the last decade and the characterization of which is still a major scientific challenge.¹⁴ Up to date, there is no “universal” technique that provides a full characterization of nanoparticles; this task thus requires a combination of different analytical techniques, if possible at all.¹⁵ Inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) operated in single-event mode shows promising features in this context.¹⁶ The theory of this technique, called single-particle (SP) ICP-MS, was first described by Degueldre *et al.* for the characterization of colloids in aqueous suspensions.¹⁷ SP-ICP-MS can simultaneously provide information on the chemical composition, size and size distribution (spherical equivalent diameter – nm), particle mass concentration (mg L^{-1}), and particle number density (particles mL^{-1}).^{18, 19} Moreover, no hardware changes have to be implemented to use

contemporary quadrupole-based ICP-MS instrumentation in single-particle mode. Only the measurement parameters, *i.e.* dwell time and data collection, and data treatment have to be adapted, thus making this approach highly accessible.²⁰⁻²²

The widespread availability of ICP-MS instrumentation has accelerated the development of SP-ICP-MS methods for the characterization of metallic nanoparticles.²³ However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, no evaluation of the possibility of using SP-ICP-MS for the detection, size characterization and quantification of MPs has ever been attempted so far. This can be related to the additional issues that have to be considered when aiming at measuring MPs using ICP-MS, such as the need of monitoring of carbon (C⁺), the ionization efficiency of which is only calculated as 1 to 5% based on the Saha equation,^{24, 25} and the introduction of relatively large and hard particulate material (within the μm range).²⁶ Different approaches have been reported on in the literature to monitor C⁺ using ICP-MS for the purpose of quantifying dissolved carbon,²⁷⁻²⁹ and these highlighted the challenges originating from the high background coming from the dissolved atmospheric CO₂ and other C-species.³⁰ In SP mode, however, an ultra-fast dwell time ($\leq 100 \mu\text{s}$) can be used to minimize the background intensity within each "time window", while preserving the intensity for the individual signal spike obtained when a MP reaches the ICP (the signal duration of each individual spike is $\approx 0.5 \text{ ms}$ in the case of nanoparticles, although a somewhat longer signal duration can be expected for μm -sized particles).^{21, 31} In this way, the signal-to-background ratio is enhanced, allowing differentiation between the MP signals and the background. Additionally, novel sample introduction setups displaying higher sample introduction efficiency, also called total sample consumption introduction systems, have been developed for the purpose of analyzing larger entities than metallic nanoparticles, such as individual cells.³²⁻³⁴ The so-called single-cell (SC) ICP-MS technique provides information on the metal content in individual cells.³⁵ SC-ICP-MS benefits from the use of specific sample introduction systems to maximize the transport efficiency, an approach that was also exploited for the introduction of MPs in ICP-MS in this work.

In this work, the knowledge gained over the last years for the characterization of nanoparticles and for the elemental analysis of individual cells using the SP- and SC-ICP-MS techniques has been combined to study for the first time the feasibility of using ICP-MS operated in single-event mode for the detection, quantification (mass concentration and particle number density) and size characterization of microplastics.

Experimental

All measurements were carried out using an Agilent 7900 quadrupole-based ICP-MS instrument (Agilent Technologies, Japan). The instrument was operated in no gas or "vented" mode and was tuned daily before every measurement session. The instrument was operated in SP mode at the lowest possible dwell time of $100 \mu\text{s}$. Data treatment was performed using the Single Nanoparticle Analysis Module of the Agilent MassHunter Workstation software. For sample introduction, a syringe-driven MVX-7100 μL Workstation (Teledyne CETAC Technologies, USA) that enables sample solution introduction at highly stable low flow rates was coupled to the ICP-MS unit by means of special Glass Expansion glassware originally designed for high-sensitivity single-cell sample introduction, as traditional sample introduction systems are designed to filter out larger droplets

and/or small entities, such as MPs, from the nebulized aerosol.³⁶ This sample introduction system comprises a high-efficiency, low-uptake concentric nebulizer, and a low-volume, on-axis laminar-flow spray chamber. To minimize the background signal, the flow rate was set at 10 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ (minimum flow rate down to 5 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$). Also, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were collected using a FEGFEI Nova NanoSEM 450 instrument operating at an acceleration voltage of 5.00 kV. The samples were mounted on an adhesive carbon tab for SEM analysis.

For method development, a commercially available solution of metal-containing polystyrene beads (2.5 μm diameter, spherical shape, 330,000 particles mL^{-1})³⁷ was purchased from Fluidigm, Inc (USA). These polymer beads are doped with lanthanide nuclides ($^{140/142}\text{Ce}$, $^{151/153}\text{Eu}$, ^{165}Ho and $^{175/176}\text{Lu}$) and are commonly used as standards for element calibration in mass cytometry.³⁸⁻⁴⁰ Additionally, uniform non-functionalized polystyrene microspheres with a nominal diameter of 1 μm (1.63×10^{11} particles mL^{-1}) were acquired from Bangs Laboratories, Inc (USA). Both polystyrene microspheres (1 and 2.5 μm) were appropriately diluted with ultra-pure water (resistivity > 18.2 $\text{M}\Omega \text{ cm}$) obtained from a Milli-Q Element water purification system (Millipore, France) to avoid the occurrence of double events (2 microspheres reaching the plasma at more or less the same time, thus producing a signal spike, the intensity of which is caused by the simultaneous ionization of both particles). All suspensions were vigorously shaken with the aid of a vortex mixer (VWR, Belgium, 1 min).

Results and discussion

To assess the feasibility of detecting MPs using ICP-MS operated in single-event mode, the best suited approach for the monitoring of C^+ needs to be selected. As a result of the high background intensity found when using the most abundant C isotope (12 amu, relative isotopic abundance of 98.93 %), the lower abundant nuclide (13 amu, relative isotopic abundance of 1.07 %) was used instead for monitoring the C content in MPs. In addition, a low flow rate of 10 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ only was selected to increase the signal-to-background ratio (MPs signal spikes *versus* background signal coming from dissolved C in each “time window”), as the sample dispense speed does not influence the intensity for the MPs signal spikes, while it decreases the contribution from the continuous background. A low flow rate was also required to achieve optimum performance when using a total sample consumption setup.

For method development, different dilutions (2-, 5- and 10-fold dilution) of the stock solution of the 2.5 μm lanthanide-doped polystyrene microspheres were prepared and for each analysis, 25 μL of solution were injected using the MVX-7100 μL Workstation. For each set of conditions, 3 measurement replicates were carried out and the microspheres were monitored *via* the $^{13}\text{C}^+$ and $^{165}\text{Ho}^+$ signal intensities (18 measurement replicates). Figure 1 shows the transient signal monitored for both isotopes. It needs to be noted that the $^{13}\text{C}^+$ spikes can be separated from the background signal (Figure 1a), thus *de facto* demonstrating for the first time that MPs can indeed be detected *via* ICP-MS relying on the monitoring of their C content. Figure 1b further illustrates this achievement, as it can be clearly seen that the signal distribution (frequency *versus* integrated intensity) of 2.5 μm polystyrene microspheres generated based on the $^{13}\text{C}^+$ signal intensities appears separated from that of the background. The number of spikes detected is related to the number of MPs in solution, although for quantification, the transport efficiency (TE) needs to be known.⁴¹ In this way, the

number-based concentration (particle number density) can be easily calculated.¹⁹ To ensure that the number of spikes detected by monitoring the $^{13}\text{C}^+$ signals corresponds to the number of MPs introduced into the ICP-MS, the results were compared to those obtained when monitoring the $^{165}\text{Ho}^+$ signals originating from the same lanthanide-doped polystyrene beads (Figures 1c and 1d show the $^{165}\text{Ho}^+$ signal intensity *versus* time and the frequency *versus* integrated intensity distribution, respectively). The results obtained are displayed in Table 1. A very good agreement between the number of polystyrene microspheres detected using both approaches ($^{13}\text{C}^+$ and $^{165}\text{Ho}^+$ monitoring) was found for all dilution factors, thus demonstrating that the number-based concentration can be calculated *via* $^{13}\text{C}^+$ monitoring, provided that the TE is known. As indicated above, the number of polystyrene beads in the stock solution was provided by the manufacturer, thus allowing the TE (%) of 2.5 μm polystyrene microspheres to be calculated. This TE was found to be $\approx 50\%$, which is in good agreement with those reported in previous works discussing the use of the same standard for TE calculation in the context of SC-ICP-MS analysis using a high-efficiency sample introduction setup.³⁷ It also needs to be noted that no significant differences were found between the different dilutions, thus excluding potential agglomeration issues, the occurrence of double events, and/or variations as a function of the nuclide monitored.

Figure 1. Transient signals (a, c) and integrated intensity distributions (b, d) obtained for 2.5 μm lanthanide-doped polystyrene microspheres measured using ICP-MS operated in single-event mode *via* the monitoring of $^{13}\text{C}^+$ and $^{165}\text{Ho}^+$.

Table 1. Number of 2.5 μm lanthanide-doped polystyrene microspheres detected and corresponding transport efficiency (TE, %) using ICP-MS operated in single-event mode and monitoring of $^{13}\text{C}^+$ or $^{165}\text{Ho}^+$.

	Number of MPs		Transport efficiency (%)		
	^{13}C	^{165}Ho	^{13}C	^{165}Ho	
Dilution 10-fold	393	416	47.6	50.4	
	410	417	49.7	50.5	
	412	406	49.9	49.2	
	Average	405	413	49.1	50.1
	SD	10	6	1.3	0.7
Dilution 5-fold	844	825	51.2	50.0	
	792	789	48.0	47.8	
	805	794	48.8	48.1	
	Average	814	803	49.3	48.6
	SD	27	20	1.6	1.2
Dilution 2-fold	1998	1997	48.4	48.4	
	2029	1976	49.2	49.2	
	2002	2114	48.5	48.5	
	Average	2010	2029	48.7	49.2
	SD	17	74	0.4	1.8

Additionally to number-based concentration results, SP-ICP-MS provides mass concentration and size distribution information on metallic nanoparticles.¹⁸ This information is obtained from the signal intensity (counts s^{-1}) recorded for each individual nanoparticle spike and is summarized within the frequency vs. integrated intensity distribution (see Figures 1b and 1d). For metallic NPs, however, the linearity existing between integrated intensity and particle volume can be lost as a result of different degrees of atomization/ionization between smaller and larger particles.^{26, 42} This could also be a serious problem for MPs characterization using single-event ICP-MS, as relatively large particles, such as 2.5 μm polystyrene microspheres, may not ionize completely into the ICP. In such case, the particle size and mass concentration would be underestimated. To evaluate the potential occurrence of this issue, 1 μm uniform non-functionalized polystyrene microspheres were measured using the same method as described above and the results thus obtained were compared to those from 2.5 μm polystyrene beads. For this comparison to be meaningful, SEM analysis of the 1 μm microspheres was carried out to obtain further insight into the size and shape of this polystyrene

particulate material. As can be seen in Figure 2, the beads were found to be highly uniform and spherical with diameters of 1 μm .

Figure 2. SEM images of 1 μm polystyrene microspheres.

After confirmation using SEM analysis, the ICP-MS results for both polystyrene microspheres of different sizes based on their C content were compared. Figure 3 shows the frequency *versus* integrated intensity distributions for 2.5 (a) and 1 μm (b) beads. It needs to be noted that for 1 μm , the MPs distribution already overlaps partially with that of the C background. However, the maximum of the signal distribution (most frequently occurring integrated intensity) can still be calculated using the Single Nanoparticle Analysis Module of the Agilent MassHunter Workstation software. The concentration of the 1 μm polystyrene microspheres in suspension was increased to better visualize the most frequently occurring integrated signal, at the cost of a higher risk of suffering from double events affecting the number-based concentration (see below).^{26, 43} The most frequently occurring integrated intensity (3 measurement replicates) obtained under these circumstances was compared to the most frequently occurring integrated intensity for 2.5 μm polystyrene microspheres (see Table 2). For spherical MPs of the same type, the ratio between the most frequently occurring integrated intensities can directly be related to the volume of the microspheres, according to equation 1.

$$\frac{volume_{2.5\mu m}}{volume_{1\mu m}} = \frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi 1.25^3}{\frac{4}{3}\pi 0.5^3} = \frac{8.181}{0.524} = 15.62 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Based on the results obtained and displayed in Table 2, the experimental ratio calculated for the most frequently occurring integrated intensities of the 2.5 and 1 μm distributions was 15.4 ± 1.4 . This indicates that no significant differences were found between the experimental ratio calculated based on the $^{13}\text{C}^+$ integrated intensities and the theoretical ratio for two spheres of 2.5 and 1 μm diameter. These results thus suggest that both microspheres are adequately handled by the ICP (the linearity is thus not affected). If not, a lower extent of atomization/ionization of the larger particles would lead to a lower experimental ratio compared to the theoretical one.

Figure 3. Integrated intensity distribution of 2.5 (a) and 1 (b) μm polystyrene microspheres based on the monitoring of $^{13}\text{C}^+$.

Table 2. Most frequently occurring intensities for 2.5 and 1 μm polystyrene microspheres obtained based on the monitoring of $^{13}\text{C}^+$.

	Diameter microspheres	
	2.5 μm	1 μm
Most frequently occurring intensity (counts.s ⁻¹)	4,464,783	282,312
Average	4,300,000	280,000
SD	200,000	22,000

Experimental ratio = 15.4 ± 1.4

Theoretical ratio = 15.62

Conclusions and future directions

In this work, microplastics – polystyrene microspheres – have been detected for the first time using ICP-MS operated in single-event mode *via* the monitoring of their carbon content ($^{13}\text{C}^+$). The accuracy of the number-based concentration values determined in this way has been studied by comparing the number of 2.5 μm lanthanide-doped polystyrene microspheres detected relying on the monitoring of $^{13}\text{C}^+$ and of $^{165}\text{Ho}^+$, respectively. Despite substantial overlap with the background distribution, also non-functionalized uniform 1 μm polystyrene microspheres have been measured using the same approach. In this context, the ratio between the most frequently occurring integrated intensities for 2.5 and 1 μm microspheres, respectively, was found to be in very good agreement with the theoretical ratio calculated based on the differences in volume between spheres of 2.5 and 1 μm diameter. These results demonstrate the possibility of characterizing MPs (spherical shape) for their mass concentration, particle number density, and size distribution within the range of study, while suggesting the possibility of using ICP-MS operated in single-event mode as a future routine technique for the detection, quantification and size characterization of MPs in water samples. However, further research is still required to optimize the method reported on in this work aiming at detecting and characterizing MPs of lower sizes and at assessing the MP size working range. In this context, instrument optimization and reduction of the background (caused by dissolved atmospheric CO_2 and other C-species present in the samples of interest) are mandatory for the establishment of this technique in environmental laboratories. Additional issues, such as suitable calibration approaches or the availability of reference MPs of different origin for further validation, have to be addressed into greater detail before ICP-MS operated in single-event mode can evolve into a routine approach for the study of MPs in environmental water samples.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare

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